

Factors affecting vegan cosmetics purchase intention of gen Z in Vietnam

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Abstract

To examine factors affecting vegan cosmetics purchase intention of Vietnamese gen Z. The study combines qualitative and quantitative methods, analyzing data from a survey of 124 young people in Vietnam, with 106 expressing an intention to buy vegan cosmetics. The collected data were analyzed using SMARTPLS software. The results, with a 95% confidence level, show that “Environmental concern” (CFE) influences “Attitude towards vegan cosmetics” (ATVC) with an impact coefficient of 0.771. The factors “Attitude towards vegan cosmetics” (ATVC) and “Perceived behavioral control” (PBC) influence “Purchase intention for vegan cosmetics” (IPVC) with impact coefficients of 0.487 and 0.392, respectively. The factor “Subjective norms” was not statistically significant in its relationship with IPVC. Based on these findings, the research provides discussions and suggestions to encourage young people to adopt environmentally friendly cosmetic products, particularly vegan cosmetics, to ensure the health and beauty of consumers.

Keywords: *Purchase intention, affecting factors affecting, Gen Z, Vietnam, cosmetics, vegan cosmetics*

1. Introduction

The cosmetics market is a rapidly growing and highly competitive industry globally. Countries with strong cosmetics markets like Japan, South Korea, Europe, and the US have also recognized Vietnam as a potential market. The trend of using natural products not tested on animals is gaining attention among the youth. Recognizing the importance of sustainable development, cosmetic brands have emerged to meet the skincare needs of Vietnamese consumers, especially the Gen Z demographic. Manufacturers are investing in research and development of high-quality vegan products to cater to the increasing demand. With rising living standards, Vietnamese women are increasingly using cosmetics for beauty care, making it an essential need. Historically, safe skincare

methods using natural herbs were known to the elite, but over time, industrially produced chemical cosmetics became prevalent due to convenience and affordability, gradually dominating the beauty industry. However, with improved income and quality of life, consumers are returning to safe, natural products that are environmentally friendly and emphasize humane values. Consequently, vegan cosmetics are becoming famous with many Vietnamese consumers. Despite the clean, eco-certified beauty products always expensive with high prices, consumers, especially Gen Z, are willing to pay a premium for the benefits these products offer.

Currently, in Vietnam, some well-known vegan cosmetic brands like Cocoon and Giọt Lành use 100% plant-based ingredients without animal derivatives, effectively meeting skincare needs and becoming increasingly popular among Gen Z consumers. This demographic values quality and environmentally friendly products, highlighting the potential market for vegan cosmetics. Factors affecting the intention to buy vegan cosmetics among the youth include environmental ethics and the importance of internal care. Environmental pollution and harmful chemical products threaten human health (Huyen Ngo Thi Ngoc, Bang Nguyen Viet Hao, Hong Thach, 2024). “Green living” not only refers to reusing plastic bags or reducing single-use plastics but also extends to the cosmetics industry. Vegan cosmetics, a significant trend in the beauty field since 2021, allow consumers to care for their skin while protecting the environment. Unlike other organic or natural cosmetics, vegan products do not contain animal-derived ingredients like bear bile, beeswax, or snail essence, nor are they tested on animals. Therefore, vegan cosmetics have attracted a large consumer base, becoming a leading segment in the beauty industry globally, including Vietnam. Recognizing the increasing popularity of vegan cosmetics among young Vietnamese consumers, the research team chose the topic “*Factors affecting vegan cosmetics purchase intention of Gen Z in Vietnam*” to identify and measure the impact of various factors on this intention. The research aims to propose solutions to promote the development of the vegan cosmetics market in Vietnam.

2. Theoretical basis and research model

2.1. Cosmetics and vegan cosmetics

Concept of cosmetics

According to Blakiston (1972), “Cosmetics are products intended for cleaning the body, enhancing beauty, increasing attractiveness, altering appearance, and protecting and nourishing external body tissues”. The Ministry of Health (2011) defines cosmetics

as “substances or preparations used to contact the external parts of the human body (skin, hair, nails, lips) or teeth and oral mucosa with the purpose of cleaning, perfuming, changing appearance, adjusting body odor, protecting, or keeping them in good condition.”

The EU EC Regulation on cosmetics defines cosmetics as any substance or mixture used to contact external parts of the human body (epidermis, hair system, nails, lips, and external genital organs) or with teeth and mucous membranes of the oral cavity, primarily for cleaning, perfuming, changing appearance, protecting, keeping them in good condition, or adjusting body odor.

Concept of vegan cosmetics

Vegan cosmetics are entirely plant-based, excluding animal derivatives or components such as eggs, milk, snail extract, or bee products (honey, beeswax). Vegan cosmetics also exclude production and testing on animals (Chrissy Callahan, 2019).

Since the 1990s, vegan cosmetics have been certified when they meet approval conditions with the Vegan seal from organizations like Vegan Action and The Vegan Society, established in 1944 in the UK by Donald Watson. Veganism, familiar to vegetarians, denotes those pursuing a vegan lifestyle, avoiding any products originating from or related to animal slaughter (Elliott Rose, 2006).

Types of vegan cosmetics

Similar to regular cosmetics, vegan cosmetics are categorized based on their function, gender, age, and method of use.

Benefits of vegan cosmetics

Vegan cosmetics are not only safe for users and environmentally friendly but also carry significant humane values for animals.

+ *Safety and mildness*: Completely plant-based extracts provide natural vitamins that nourish healthy skin without side effects or skin diseases. Vegan cosmetics are safe even for the most sensitive skin, such as babies’ or pregnant women’s skin.

+ *Health protection*: Natural ingredients prevent skin dryness, clogging pores, or causing irritation. They are free from lead, phthalates, and sodium laureth sulfate, which are harmful chemicals linked to health issues like cancer and skin irritation. Besides beautifying, natural herbs also have medicinal properties, reducing stress and stimulating nerves.

+*Environmental protection*: Avoiding animal-derived ingredients reduces the need for livestock farming, saving water, mitigating climate change causes, and reducing pollution.

+*Humane values*: By not harming animals for ingredients, vegan cosmetics do not affect animals' living environments or expose factory workers to harmful chemicals.

2.2. Vietnamese Gen Z and consuming behavior

Gen Z

Gen Z follows previous generations like X and Y, born between the mid-1990s and 2012. They were exposed to technology early and have advanced thinking in finance, economy, and technology, capable of significantly affecting the future (Bui Tuan An, n.d.).

Consuming behavior of Vietnamese Gen Z

Gen Z is a smart consumer group, thanks to their proficiency in information technology, allowing them to research and evaluate products easily. They often rely on reviews from social media influencers like KOLs and influencers. When shopping online, they meticulously examine their needs and product suitability through websites, e-commerce platforms, or mobile apps, considering detailed user reviews.

Moreover, Gen Z tends to prioritize environmentally friendly products. Their shopping behavior is trend-driven rather than based on essential needs. Hence, understanding current consumer trends and young people's purchase intentions is crucial for businesses (Trang Vu, n.d.).

2.3. Theoretical basis

Consumer behavior

Consumer behavior encompasses actions and decisions made by individuals or households when selecting, purchasing, using, and disposing of products or services (Bhat, 2021). It integrates ideas from psychology, biology, chemistry, and economics to understand how personal motivations, perceptions, and attitudes shape consumer purchasing decisions. Economic theory explains how consumers allocate limited resources among competing needs, guiding businesses in pricing and product positioning strategies (Radu, 2023).

Purchase intention

Purchase intention reflects customers' readiness to buy a specific product or use a specific service, influenced by both external and internal factors. It measures respondents' attitudes towards purchasing goods or services (MBA Skool Team, 2021). Understanding purchase intention helps companies design focused advertising campaigns and marketing messages to boost sales and customer loyalty (Bhasin, 2023).

Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA)

TRA model examines consumer behavior, identifying their behavioral intentions based on attitudes towards the behavior and subjective norms (influences from others). It predicts and explains behavioral tendencies better than attitudes towards products or services (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975).

Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

TPB, an extension of TRA by Ajzen (1991), is widely used to predict specific individual behaviors, including product or service purchase decisions. It considers attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control (individual perceptions of ease or difficulty in performing a behavior, including necessary resources, knowledge, and opportunities) (Ajzen, 1991).

2.4. Research Overview

Many empirical research, conducted in Vietnam, have determined the elements affecting the attitudes and actions of consumers, including young people, when it comes to buying cosmetics across a variety of market categories, including natural and organic cosmetics. Studies that focus exclusively on vegan cosmetics are, however, quite rare. Most of them discuss the general trend of young people or consumers using vegan cosmetics, but they don't go into detail into the variables affecting this group's inclination to use these products.

The study conducted by Phuong Nguyen (2024) underscores the significance of the vegan cosmetics market and acknowledges its enormous potential. In addition to serving as a marketplace, the Vietnamese market serves as a supply base for the raw ingredients needed to make vegan cosmetics. The research is divided into six chapters. In chapter 1, the concept of cosmetics, its qualities, and the ways in which brands set themselves apart from traditional cosmetics are all examined and analyzed. It talks about the features and difficulties of the vegan cosmetics market in Vietnam. In particular, chapter 4 discusses what influences people's decisions to buy vegan makeup. The aim of

the study is to determine the elements that facilitate vegan cosmetic brands to reach consumers in different areas and to examine the growth of vegan cosmetics in Vietnam. By doing this, brands are able to take use of their advantages and maintain their place in the fiercely competitive home cosmetics market while expanding internationally.

Nguyen Ngoc Minh Duyen's research (2020) on the factors affecting green cosmetics purchasing behavior of Finnish gen Z. By using qualitative and quantitative research methodology, including data from 67 Finnish respondents between the ages of 15 and 25. The study's findings revealed a number of variables that affect consumers' decision-making processes while making purchases, such as perceived consumer efficacy, behavioral control, eco-labeling and certification, and social and subjective norms. The study found that while the research data supports the hypotheses that eco-labeling and certification, subjective norms/social norms, reference groups, and perceived consumer effectiveness have a significant positive influence on Generation Z consumers' green cosmetic purchases, the research data does not support the hypothesis that perceived behavioral control has a positive influence on Finnish Generation Z customers' future intentions to consume green cosmetics. Some management implications for green cosmetics manufacturers and marketers were developed based on the research findings.

The study conducted in 2021 by Luu Phuong Quynh and Nguyen Thi Truc Ngan examined the influence of brand awareness and additional factors on the intention of women in Ho Chi Minh City to consume cosmetics. The findings demonstrated that perceptions of four factors-design, perceived quality, subjective norms, and brand awareness-have an impact on consumers' intentions to consume. The "design" component had the biggest influence out of all of these.

In their 2021 study, Nguyen Hoai Tu Nguyen and Nguyen Thi Bich Ngoc examined the variables affecting the cosmetics purchase intentions of female Generation Z consumers in Ho Chi Minh City. Price, product, sales promotion, brand, attitude, and reference groups are some of these variables. After gathering 300 responses from female Generation Z consumers in Ho Chi Minh City, statistical analysis, reliability testing, factor analysis, regression analysis, and correlation analysis were performed using SPSS. The study found that among female Generation Z consumers in Ho Chi Minh City, all variables (price, product, sales promotion, brand, attitude, and reference groups) strongly correlated with the intention to purchase cosmetics. Of these, brand, price, product, and reference groups had the most effects on purchase intention; attitude and sales promotion

had the least effects.

Based on the theory of planned behavior model, Nguyen Thi Quynh Nga and Le Dang Nhu Huynh's (2019) study examined the variables affecting organic cosmetics purchase intentions of customers in Ho Chi Minh City. Five independent variables are included in the suggested research model: environmental awareness, quality awareness, safety value awareness, health awareness, and subjective norms. Using quantitative research methods and a sample survey of 200 consumers, the findings indicated that all five criteria affected consumers' desire to buy, with safety value awareness having the most influence.

In two significant Vietnamese cities, Hanoi and Ho Chi Minh City, the researchers found factors that directly influenced customers' inclination to purchase vegan cosmetics. The findings showed that respondents' intentions to purchase vegan cosmetics were significantly positively impacted by all three TPB components. Moreover, trust and perceived knowledge were positively correlated with attitude and perceived behavioral control, while environmental concern had a substantial impact on all TPB variables. This study offers crucial information that businesses and marketers can use to comprehend the variables affecting consumers' purchase intentions and select winning tactics in Vietnam's vegan cosmetics sector.

There are also more studies from other nations mentioned. Eun-Hee Park and In-Hee Lee's research from 2021 revealed the variables affecting people's decisions to buy vegan cosmetics. The subfactors of consumption value, such as functional value, economic value, social value, conditional value, epistemic value, and emotional value, were significantly influenced by the careful type and adaptive type of consumer decision-making types when they were higher in the effects of consumer decision-making types on the consumption value of vegan cosmetics. Although the demand for natural cosmetics is driven by consumers' desire for a sustainable and healthy lifestyle, the different promises made about natural cosmetics leave consumers perplexed and wary. This study used the planned behavior (TPB) theory to investigate the variables affecting customers' decisions to buy natural cosmetics. Purposive sampling is a qualitative method used in this investigation. Data were collected and analyzed from 21 Uppsala residents who were either traditional or natural cosmetics consumers using semi-structured interview approaches and thematic analysis. The findings indicated that: consumers' attitudes toward purchasing natural cosmetics were ambiguous and did not clearly influence their

behavior; perceived social pressures from friends, family, and groups, on the other hand, had a definite positive influence on their behavior; online shopping, referrals from others, and living a sustainable lifestyle encouraged their behavior; and high prices, difficult locations to purchase from, ignorance, inconsistent certifications, etc., caused a discrepancy between consumers' intention to purchase and their actual behavior. Product expertise was examined as a crucial resource that customers require.

2.5. Research hypotheses and measurement scales

Research Model and Hypotheses

Figure 1. Proposed Research Model

Source: Research team proposal

Research hypotheses

H1: Attitude towards vegan cosmetics (ATVC) positively correlates with purchase intention for vegan cosmetics (IPVC)

Measurement scale for ATVC:

ATVC1. I am interested in vegan cosmetics products

ATVC2. I believe buying vegan cosmetics offers many benefits

ATVC3. I feel buying vegan cosmetics satisfies my passion

ATVC4. I feel buying vegan cosmetics is a popular trend among young people today

ATVC5. I believe buying vegan cosmetics is something young people should experience

H2: Subjective norm (SS) positively correlates with purchase intention for vegan cosmetics (IPVC)

Measurement scale for SS:

SS1. Friends and people around me advise me to buy vegan cosmetics

SS2. Important people in my life approve of my decision to buy vegan cosmetics

SS3. My interactions with others influence my purchase of eco-friendly products

SS4. I buy vegan cosmetics because friends and family intend to or already use these products

H3: Perceived behavioral control (PBC) positively correlates with purchase intention for vegan cosmetics (IPVC)

Measurement scale for PBC

PBC1. I can afford to buy vegan cosmetics

PBC2. I have the financial means to buy vegan cosmetics

PBC3. I have enough time to learn about and buy vegan cosmetics

PBC4. I am willing to spend time and money to buy vegan cosmetics

H4: Environmental concern (CFE) positively correlates with attitude towards vegan cosmetics (IPVC)

Measurement scale for CFE:

CFE1. I buy vegan cosmetics because they are environmentally friendly

CFE2. To survive, humans must maintain a balanced relationship with nature

CFE3. When consuming, I focus on eco-friendly products

CFE4. Protecting the ecosystem of green brands aligns with my ethical values

Measurement scale for IPVC:

IPVC1. I intend to buy vegan cosmetics in the future

IPVC2. I will pay more attention to buying vegan cosmetics

IPVC3. I am willing to recommend vegan cosmetics to friends and family

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Data collection method

To examine “Factors affecting vegan cosmetics purchase intention of gen Z in Vietnam”, the research team used two methods: desk research (reviewing published materials) and sociological surveys (collecting responses from targeted individuals). Data were analyzed using Excel and SMARTPLS software.

In the desk research method, the team reviewed materials on vegan cosmetics, articles on factors affecting the purchase intention of cosmetics in general and vegan cosmetics in particular among Vietnamese youth, and characteristics of Vietnamese Gen Z. The team then developed a survey questionnaire to conduct a sociological survey on factors affecting vegan cosmetics purchase intention of Gen Z in Vietnam.

In the sociological survey method, the team conducted preliminary surveys and discussions with individuals interested in or using vegan cosmetics. Participants freely expressed their views on various aspects of vegan cosmetics. The preliminary sample size was 10 people. The results of the preliminary study were used to finalize the research questionnaire and model. The team then distributed and collected surveys via a Google Form: (https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLScKkBVQT9J_CQpPgWzGjeWzvwea bFHalmZ9b23uyr1VZcQwA/viewform) to Vietnamese Gen Z.

The data collection method involved convenience sampling and the “snowball” method to ensure sufficient sample size. A total of 124 surveys were collected, with 106 valid responses indicating an intention to buy vegan cosmetics.

3.2. Data Analysis Method

Quantitative research methods were used to process the collected survey data on factors affecting Gen Z’s purchase intention for vegan cosmetics in Vietnam.

SMARTPLS software was used to test hypotheses and evaluate the impact of factors.

Step 1: Evaluation of Measurement Model

The measurement model was evaluated by examining the outer loadings, Cronbach’s Alpha, convergence, and discriminant validity.

Step 2: Evaluation of Structural Model

After meeting measurement model requirements, the structural model was evaluated through path relationships, overall R-squared values, and effect size coefficients.

4. Research Results

4.1. Descriptive Statistics of Survey Participants

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of survey participants

Gender	Number of people	Percentage (%)	Income	Number of people	Percentage (%)
Male	21	16.9	Under 1 million VND	21	16.9
Female	101	81.5	1 to under 3 million VND	35	28.2
Not specified	2	1.6	3 to under 5 million VND	26	21
Total	124	100	5 to under 10 million VND	18	14.5
Education level	Number of people	Percentage (%)	10 to under 15 million VND	5	4
Middle school	2	1.6	15 to under 20 million VND	3	2.4
High school	9	7.3	Over 20 million VND	16	12.9
University	98	79	<i>Total</i>	124	100
Postgraduate	3	2.4	Awareness of vegan cosmetics	Number of people	Percentage (%)
Working	12	9.7	Yes	109	87.9
<i>Total</i>	124	100	No	15	12.1
Area of residence	Number of people	Percentage (%)	<i>Total</i>	124	100
Urban	82	66.1	Purchased vegan cosmetics	Number of people	Percentage (%)
Suburban	42	33.9	Yes	93	85.3
<i>Total</i>	124	100	No	16	14.7
			<i>Total</i>	109	100

Source: The research result

The respondents' education level: Among the 124 participants, 2 are enrolled in secondary education (1.6%), 9 are in high school (7.3%), 98 are in university (79%), 3 are pursuing graduate degrees (2.4%), and 12 are employed at the moment (9.7%).

The respondents' gender: Of the 124 participants, 101 (81.5%) are female, 21 (16.9%) are male, and 2 (1.6%) did not indicate their gender.

The respondents' residential area: Of the 124 participants, 82 (66.1%) reside in cities, and 42 (33.9%) in suburbs.

The respondents' monthly income: Twenty-one of the 124 participants earn less than one million VND per month (16.9%); thirty-five earn between one and three million VND (28.2%); twenty-six earn between three and five million VND (21%); eighteen earn between five and ten million VND (14.5%); five earn between ten and fifteen million VND (4%); three earn between fifteen and twenty million VND (2.4%); and sixteen earn more than twenty million VND (12.9%).

The awareness of vegan products: Among the 124 survey participants, 109 people answered yes (87.9%); and 15 people answered no (12.1%).

The number of participants use or never use vegan products: Of the 109 individuals who are aware of vegan cosmetics, 85.3% have used them or are currently using them, while 14.7% have not.

4.2. The trend of consuming vegan cosmetics among Vietnamese Gen Z youth

Figure 2. Vegan cosmetic brands

Source: The research result

Of the 93 respondents, 83 knew about Cocoon Vietnam (88.2%); 17 knew about Sukin - a vegan cosmetic brand in Australia (18.3%); 13 knew about Melixir Korea (14%); 31 knew about The Body Shop - a natural cosmetic brand from England (33.3%); 62 knew about Klairs - a brand from Korea (66.7%); 19 knew about I'm from - a natural cosmetic brand from Korea (20.4%); 25 knew about Aromatica - a vegan cosmetic brand from Korea (26.9%); and 1 person had another answer (1.1%).

Figure 3. Types of vegan cosmetic products purchased

Source: The research result

Of the 93 respondents, 56 purchased Facial Cleanser (62.2%); 18 purchased Vegan Toothpaste (20%); 38 purchased Sunscreen (42.2%); 44 purchased Shampoo (48.9%); 33 purchased Vegan Hair Conditioner (36.7%); 24 purchased Body Wash (26.7%); 34 purchased Lipstick (37.8%); 16 purchased Powder (17.8%); 28 purchased Moisturizing Mask (31.1%); and 10 gave other answers (11%).

Figure 4. Frequency of using vegan cosmetic products

Source: The research result

Out of the 93 participants in the poll, 4.4% reported seldom using vegan goods, 23.3% reported occasionally using them, 38.9% reported using vegan cosmetic items with a typical frequency, 27.8% reported frequently using them, and 5.6% reported using them very frequently.

Figure 5. Reasons for using vegan cosmetic products

Source: The research result

Out of the 93 respondents to the study, 51 individuals, accounting for 55.4% of the total, reported using vegan cosmetic products for ethical reasons. A total of 59 individuals actively choose to avoid dangerous components, which accounts for 64.1% of the population. A total of 42 individuals utilize the product due to its higher nutrient content, accounting for 45.7% of the user base. Additionally, 46 users are attracted to the product's Eco-friendly vegan packaging, constituting 50% of the total users. Furthermore, 64 people employ the product for safety reasons, representing 69.6% of the user population. A total of 69 individuals prefer to select items that are made from natural components, which accounts for 75% of the total. A total of 37 individuals, accounting for 40.2% of the population, utilize anti-aging products. A total of 42 individuals, accounting for 45.7% of the respondents, consider this product to be the ultimate solution for sensitive skin. Additionally, 36 individuals, representing 39.1% of the respondents, use this product with the intention of safeguarding the ecosystem. Lastly, a small minority of 3 individuals, comprising 3.3% of the respondents, cited additional reasons for using this product.

Figure 6. Future intentions to use vegan cosmetic products

Source: The research result

Among the 109 respondents, 106 (or 97.2%) expressed a desire to keep using vegan cosmetic products, whereas 3 (2.8% of the total) expressed a non-interest. Looking at the numbers, it's clear that most people who took the poll plan to keep using vegan cosmetics.

4.3. Results of testing the factors affecting vegan cosmetics purchase intention of Vietnamese Gen Z

4.3.1. Results of assessing the quality of observed variables in the measurement model

Checking the quality of observed variables

The quality of observed variables is assessed through the outer loadings. In the initial data run, the ATVC1, CFE2, CFE4, SS3, SS4 scales had outer loadings less than 0.7, so the ATVC1, CFE2, CFE4, SS3, SS4 scales were eliminated from the model. The research team reran the data for the second time to evaluate the quality of observed variables affecting the intention to buy vegan cosmetics, which is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Outer loadings of factors affecting the intention to purchase vegan cosmetics of Vietnamese Gen Z

	ATVC	CFE	IPVC	PBC	SS
ATVC2	0.859				
ATVC3	0.833				
ATVC4	0.895				
ATVC5	0.903				
CFE1		0.955			
CFE3		0.957			
IPVC1			0.938		
IPVC2			0.930		
IPVC3			0.928		
PBC1				0.917	
PBC2				0.915	
PBC3				0.898	
PBC4				0.912	
SS1					0.952
SS2					0.952

Source: Test results of the research team

The results from Table 2 show that the outer loadings of all the total variable correlation coefficients of the variables affecting the intention to purchase vegan cosmetics (all > 0.7) (Hair & et al, 2016) show that the observed variables are significant.

Testing the reliability of the scale

Assessing the reliability of the scale of factors affecting the intention to buy vegan cosmetics on SMARTPLS through two main indexes: Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (CR).

Table 3. Reliability coefficient (Cronbach's Alpha) and composite reliability (Composite Reliability) of factors affecting the intention to purchase vegan cosmetics

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
ATVC	0.896	0.898	0.928	0.762
CFE	0.906	0.906	0.955	0.914
IPVC	0.924	0.925	0.952	0.869
PBC	0.931	0.933	0.951	0.829
SS	0.896	0.896	0.951	0.906

Source: Test results of the research team

According to Table 3, after analyzing the reliability test using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of the factor, the results show that all scales satisfy the condition > 0.7 (DeVellis, 2012) and do not violate any rule of eliminating variables, so no variables are eliminated and can be accepted in terms of reliability. The composite reliability (CR) of all observed variables is also > 0.7 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988) (Table 3). Therefore, the scale is reliable, has analytical significance and is used in the next factor analysis.

The convergence

According to the data analysis results in Table 3, the average variance extracted (AVE) index of all variables is > 0.5 (Hock & Ringle, 2010), which shows that the model satisfies the convergence conditions.

Differential Validity

The results in Table 4 on the Fornell-Larcker index of the research model of factors affecting the intention to buy vegan cosmetics all ensure discrimination because all the square root values of AVE on the diagonal are higher than their off-diagonal values. Therefore, in terms of discrimination value, the two criteria including cross-loading factor and Fornell and Larcker criteria have met the conditions.

Table 4. Fornell-Larcker of the research model of factors affecting the intention to buy vegan cosmetics of Vietnamese Gen Z youth

	ATVC	CFE	IPVC	PBC	SS
ATVC	0.873				
CFE	0.771	0.956			
IPVC	0.791	0.735	0.932		
PBC	0.740	0.707	0.765	0.911	
SS	0.761	0.676	0.659	0.688	0.952

Source: Test results of the research team

f² function value

The f^2 value represents the effect size of a construct (factor) when it is removed from the model. The f^2 values of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 correspond to small, medium, and large effects (Cohen, 1988) of the exogenous variable. If the effect size is less than 0.02, it is considered to have no effect.

Table 5. Summary table of f^2 Values

	ATVC	CFE	IPVC	PBC	SS
ATVC			0.261		
CFE	1.463				
IPVC					
PBC			0.211		
SS			0.000		

Source: Test results of the research team

In this model, Table 5 shows:

Impact on ATVC: The f^2 value of the CFE variable is 1.463 (f^2 value > 0.35), indicating that the influence of CFE on ATVC is large.

Impact on IPVC: The f^2 values of the ATVC and PBC variables are 0.261 and 0.211, respectively, indicating that the influence of these variables on IPVC is medium ($0.15 < f^2 < 0.35$). The f^2 value of the SS variable is 0.000, indicating that this variable has no impact on IPVC (f^2 value < 0.02).

4.3.2. Impact assessment results using structural model

Assessing influential relationships

The relationship and level of influence of factors affecting the intention to buy vegan cosmetics of Vietnamese Gen Z youth on SMARTPLS is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Factors affecting the intention to purchase vegan cosmetics of Vietnamese Gen Z youth

Source: Research team's SMARTPLS testing results

Impact on ATVC: The variable “Environmental concern” (CFE) influences the variable “Attitude towards vegan cosmetics” (ATVC) with an impact coefficient of 0.771 and a P Value < 0.05, indicating that the CFE factor is statistically significant in reflecting the relationship to ATVC (Hypothesis H4 is accepted).

Impact on IPVC: The variables “Attitude towards vegan cosmetics” (ATVC) with an impact coefficient of 0.487 and “Perceived behavioral control” (PBC) with an impact coefficient of 0.392 have P Values < 0.05, indicating that these factors are statistically significant in reflecting a positive relationship to the purchase intention of vegan cosmetics (Hypotheses H1, H3 are accepted). The variable “Subjective norms” (SS) has a P Value > 0.05, indicating it is not statistically significant in reflecting a relationship to the purchase intention of vegan cosmetics (Hypothesis H2 is not accepted).

Table 6. Path Coefficient of the structural model

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
ATVC -> IPVC	0.487	0.489	0.124	3.924	0.000
CFE -> ATVC	0.771	0.773	0.049	15.890	0.000
CFE -> IPVC	0.375	0.380	0.106	3.543	0.000
PBC -> IPVC	0.392	0.390	0.127	3.082	0.002
SS -> IPVC	0.019	0.023	0.112	0.172	0.864

Source: Research team's SMARTPLS testing results

The test results in Table 6 show that with 95% confidence, we can get the regression equation as follows:

$$\text{ATVC} = 0.771 * \text{CFE}$$

$$\text{IPVC} = 0.487 * \text{ATVC} + 0.392 * \text{PBC}$$

Evaluate the overall coefficient of determination R^2 (R square)

The result of PLS Algorithm analysis gives R^2 value, reflecting the level of explanation of the independent variable for the dependent variable. R^2 index measures the overall coefficient of determination (R-square value), which is an index to measure the level of model fit of the data (the explanatory ability of the model). According to Hair & et al (2010) suggested R-square value at 0.75, 0.50 or 0.25.

Table 7. Coefficient of the level of explanation of the independent variable for the dependent variable (R Square)

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
ATVC	0.594	0.590
IPVC	0.698	0.689

Source: Research team's testing results

The results from Table 7 show:

The variable ATVC: R^2 is 0.594 and the adjusted R^2 is 0.590, indicating that the CFE variable in the model explains 59.4% of the variance in the ATVC variable.

The variable *IPVC*: R^2 is 0.698 and the adjusted R^2 is 0.689, indicating that the *ATVC* and *PBC* variables explain 68.9% of the variance in the *IPVC* variable.

Assessment of Reliability Index (SRMR)

The Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) index indicates the fit of the research model. According to Hu & Bentler (1999), a model is typically considered a good fit if the SRMR value is less than 0.08 or 0.1.

Table 8. Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) Reliability Index

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.042	0.096

Source: Research team's testing results

The SRMR results in Table 8 of the research model show that the Saturated Model has an SRMR of 0.042, which is smaller than 0.08; and the estimated model has an SRMR of 0.096, which is smaller than 0.1. Therefore, this model is suitable for data analysis.

5. Discussion

The research results indicate that with 95% confidence, the variable “Environmental concern” (CFE) influences the variable “*Attitude towards vegan cosmetics*” (*ATVC*) with an impact coefficient of 0.771. This shows that when environmental concern increases by 1 unit, the attitude towards vegan cosmetics increases by 0.771 units. Among the two factors affecting the “*Purchase intention for vegan cosmetics*” (*IPVC*), the factor “*Attitude towards vegan cosmetics*” (*ATVC*) has the strongest impact on “*Purchase intention for vegan cosmetics*” (*IPVC*) with an impact coefficient of 0.487. This indicates that when the attitude of young people towards vegan cosmetics increases by 1 unit, the purchase intention increases by 0.487 units. Next is the factor “*Perceived behavioral control*” (*PBC*), which has an impact coefficient of 0.392 on the purchase intention for vegan cosmetics, showing that when perceived behavioral control increases by 1 unit, the purchase intention for vegan cosmetics increases by 0.392 units.

(1) The factor “*Attitude towards vegan cosmetics*” has the strongest impact on the “Purchase intention for vegan cosmetics” of young Vietnamese people. This shows that attitudes towards any information related to vegan cosmetics, such as origin and input materials, greatly influence the vegan cosmetics purchase intention of Vietnamese Gen Z.

Figure 8. The mean scores of the observed variables of the variable “Attitude towards vegan cosmetic products”

Source: Survey results

The survey results show that the observed variables ATVC1, ATVC2, ATVC4, and ATVC5 of the variable “Attitude Towards Vegan Cosmetic Products” are all at the “strongly agree” response threshold, with values ranging from 4.264 to 4.387, while the observed variable ATVC3 is at the “agree” response threshold (4.085).

(2) The factor “*Subjective norms*”, although the quantitative results indicate that the “Subjective norms” factor is not statistically significant in affecting the “Purchase intention for vegan cosmetics,” the survey results suggest that subjective norms do have some impact on consumers’ thoughts regarding the intention to purchase vegan cosmetics.

Figure 9. Average score of observed variables of the variable “Subjective norms”

Source: Survey results

The survey results show that the observed variables SS1, SS2, SS3, and SS4 of the variable “Subjective norms” are all at the “agree” response threshold, with values ranging from 4.019 to 4.104.

(3) The factor “*Perceived behavioral control*” has an impact on the “Purchase intention for vegan cosmetics” at a level of 0.392, indicating that the financial and personal capabilities of Vietnamese Gen Z play an important role in their purchase intention.

Figure 10. The average score of the observed variables of the variable “Perceived behavioral control”

Source: Survey results

The survey results show that the observed variables PBC2, PBC3, and PBC4 of the variable “*Perceived behavioral control*” are all at the “agree” response threshold, with values ranging from 4.142 to 4.17. Only the observed variable PBC1 is at the “strongly agree” response threshold (4.208).

(4) The factor “*Environmental concern*” has a positive impact on the intention, indicating that environmentally friendly vegan cosmetic products attract young Vietnamese Gen Z consumers and increase their interest in these new cosmetic lines.

Figure 11. The average score of the observed variables of the variable “Environmental concern”

Source: Survey results

The survey results show that the observed variables CFE1, CFE2, CFE3, and CFE4 of the variable “*Environmental concern*” are all at the “strongly agree” response threshold, with values ranging from 4.34 to 4.394.

Based on the collected results, the research team provides some discussion points to promote awareness and consciousness among young people about consuming environmentally friendly green cosmetic products in general and vegan cosmetics in particular as follows:

The factor “*Attitude towards vegan cosmetics*” has the strongest impact on the purchase intention for vegan cosmetics. This indicates that the initial impression of customers or their attitudes towards this type of cosmetics plays a crucial role in driving the purchase intention for vegan cosmetics among Vietnamese Gen Z. Therefore, manufacturers or distributors of vegan cosmetics should pay special attention to the quality, design, diversity, and especially the impression of humaneness and environmental friendliness to create a positive attitude from consumers towards vegan cosmetics, thereby stimulating the purchase intention of Vietnamese Gen Z. Specifically, the factor “*Environmental concern*” impacts the attitude towards vegan cosmetics. Thus, to change young people’s attitudes towards vegan cosmetics and promote their consumption habits, it is necessary to focus on the factor “Environmental concern”. Companies should organize social and humanitarian programs discussing the importance of environmental concern and the awareness of young people towards the environment. They can collaborate with influencers and schools to promote activities such as “The Origin of green cosmetic products”, “How chemical cosmetics harm the environment and animals”, “The Humanity in the beauty industry and its potential savings”, “How green cosmetics affect the body, health, and beauty compared to conventional chemical

cosmetics”, using high-impact visual posters and videos. This will attract young people’s interest in the environment and positively affect their attitude towards vegan cosmetics. When interest is sufficiently high, it will lead to a positive attitude towards the product and drive the purchase intention for vegan cosmetics.

Perceived behavioral control also positively impacts the purchase intention for vegan cosmetics among Vietnamese young people. Therefore, manufacturers need to thoroughly understand and explore consumer conditions, particularly young people’s financial capabilities and potential, to segment customers and offer suitable product segments for each individual’s and group’s capability. When young people have sufficient potential and ability to purchase products that match their needs and potential, they will likely buy vegan cosmetics in the future, thereby promoting the purchase intention for environmentally friendly and vegan cosmetics.

Although the factor “*Subjective norms*” is not statistically significant to conclude its impact on the purchase intention for vegan cosmetics, it is undeniable that the influence of those around them has a certain impact on the long-term purchase intention for vegan cosmetics. This is because today’s youth, primarily Gen Z, tend to consume based on trends and are easily influenced by the consumption behavior of those around them, especially friends, family, and influencers. Therefore, to promote the purchase intention and behavior towards vegan cosmetics, manufacturers should collaborate with brands, KOLs, and KOCs through affiliate marketing to deeply influence Gen Z consumers. When choosing influencers to promote green, organic, and especially vegan cosmetics, it will encourage young people to trust and use these products more in the future with a variety of environmentally friendly green products.

6. Conclusion

This research identifies factors affecting the purchase intention for vegan cosmetics among Vietnamese Gen Z. Through survey results and data analyzed using a combination of qualitative and quantitative research methods, the research team identifies the factors and their impact on the purchase intention for vegan cosmetics among Vietnamese youth. The research results align with previous empirical studies and also contribute by providing discussions to promote the purchase and consumption of vegan cosmetics in particular and green cosmetic products in general, aiming to improve environmental quality, pursue green and sustainable development, and ensure consumer health and beauty safety.

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